

PRAGMATICS AND LANGUAGE REGISTERS IN TEACHING AND LEARNING FOR RWANDAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

This study explores the role of pragmatics and language registers in teaching and learning Kinyarwanda in Rwandan secondary schools. It is based on the hypothesis that both teachers and students struggle to effectively use formal Kinyarwanda, whether in speech or writing, due to a limited understanding of pragmatic principles, such as context, purpose, and appropriateness of language use.

Adopting both cognitive and communicative approaches, the study employs a mixed-methods design, combining data from classroom observations and questionnaires.

The findings indicate that integrating pragmatic awareness and language registers significantly enhances teaching effectiveness and student comprehension. However, the lack of teaching materials on these topics remains a key challenge. Teachers and students recommended stronger collaboration between the Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy (RCHA) and the Ministry of Education to promote the effective use and preservation of formal Kinyarwanda.

INTRODUCTION

Since 2015, Rwanda has shifted from the Knowledge-Based Curriculum to the Competence-Based Curriculum, and some changes in Kinyarwanda writing were introduced by the ministerial order to mark instructions governing the orthography of Kinyarwanda since 2014. However, Kinyarwanda teachers acknowledge poor speech and orthography among the youth students. This is due to many code shifts and unnecessary word borrowing from neighboring countries' languages or foreign languages like French and English. One of the solutions to this problem is the integration of pragmatics and language registers in teaching

and learning at all levels of classroom learning in secondary schools. There is a strong report of limited resources and training in integrating pragmatic principles into their teaching practices. In developing countries like Rwanda, education is all that matters to reach the rapid standard of the country's adequate development in all life. According to many writings from most of the researchers, like Canagarajah, as cited in Mukama & Nkusi (2019, p. 24), languages have nothing to do with wars between them, but their complementarity is essential for interaction and effective communication.

Since the introduction of the Ministerial Instructions on the Orthography of Kinyarwanda (No. 001/2014, issued on October 8, 2014), which aimed to standardize formal Kinyarwanda, challenges have persisted, particularly among secondary school students. Despite these official efforts, many students continue to struggle with proper usage, suggesting that orthographic regulation alone is insufficient. This difficulty is compounded by the limited integration of pragmatic strategies and language registers into classroom instruction. Pragmatic competence, as the ability to adjust language use according to context, audience, and purpose, is essential for effective communication but remains underemphasized in both teaching and teacher training.

The lack of attention to pragmatics and language registers in the curriculum has led to a gap in students' ability to navigate different communicative situations, ultimately affecting their academic performance and cultural literacy. Addressing this issue requires not only policy reform but also pedagogical innovation. Teaching practices that include pragmatic awareness and appropriate use of language registers can support more meaningful learning, foster deeper student engagement, and promote the transmission of Rwandan culture through formal education.

In response, this study proposes to investigate how pragmatics and language registers are currently applied in the teaching and learning of Kinyarwanda in secondary schools. It aims to identify existing gaps and offer recommendations to strengthen instructional strategies that enhance both linguistic competence and cultural preservation.

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on Kinyarwanda language instruction in five purposively selected secondary schools across Rwanda. Limitations were influenced by the study scale of students and teachers from 9/12YBE of all four corners in Rwanda. The selection of schools aimed to ensure geographic representation but did not include private or vocational schools. Those participants were purposively selected based on their exposure to Kinyarwanda instruction.

Literature Review

Pragmatics and language registers use and integration in a classroom setting can play a great role in shaping students' learning experiences and performance in national exams, public speaking, debates and discussions, drama, and adaptability to the sustainability of the Rwandan culture in general. In Rwandan secondary schools, the interaction between teachers and students is formal in general, but when it comes to students outside the classroom with their peers, a heavy influence of foreign languages begins to arise and results in many infected forms of Kinyarwanda formal speech and orthography. As we emphasized the importance of Pragmatics and Language registers integration in teaching and learning, we have raised a

concern based on the fact that students do not formally apply Kinyarwanda in a classroom setting, and this leads to a lack of educational success and best practices in Kinyarwanda as a language and cradle of Rwandan culture.

Kinyarwanda is a Bantu language spoken primarily in Rwanda, and some parts of neighboring countries like Uganda, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Burundi, and Tanzania. As Zeller, & Ngoboka (2015: p.207) confirm, Kinyarwanda is classified under D 61 of the Bantu languages. Botne (1990: p.190) says, "In general, the three languages of J6l-Kinyarwanda, Kirundi, and Giha show very close correspondences in form and meaning in most verbal constructions." He mentioned this according to the Tervuren classification, which puts Kinyarwanda in this linguistic family.

Kinyarwanda is one of the official languages of Rwanda, alongside Kiswahili, French, and English. They are all equal in being official languages and have equal rights status. Niyomugabo (2019, p 89) says, "All the times Kinyarwanda was a language that unified local leaders and the population during the monarchial rule. The traditional Rwandan community used to have specific and formal organs in charge of promoting the Kinyarwanda language. In this context, two organs can be mentioned: the evening gathering "Igitaramo" and "Itorero," which was a Rwandan traditional school."

Samuelson & Freedman (2010, p.192) say, "Policymakers in Rwanda see the new language policy as a major factor in the success of Rwanda's post-genocide reforms. We see the reforms as also risky and wish to employ this situation as a case study for the impact of globalization on the study of English worldwide. The Rwandan government is justifying the switch to English as a medium of instruction by pointing to the global and regional growth of English as the leading language of science, commerce, and economic development." On the other hand, Kinyarwanda remains a course that crosses all levels of education, from primary schools to universities. In Rwanda and Uganda, we share the same language of instruction, "English," although it is not the official language in Uganda. (Nassenstein, 2016, p.396). In modern times, Rwanda has adopted English as a language of instruction to replace French. This decision reflects a commitment to promoting linguistic and cultural identity, as per notice the National census statistics indicate that Kinyarwanda is a mother tongue, national language, and official language after analyzing since more than 85% of the Rwandan population speaks Kinyarwanda only (NISR, 2022).

Nowadays, educational institutions in Rwanda provide schooling for students between the ages of 12 and 19, covering grades 7 to 12, which means that after passing a Primary six National Exam m they attend secondary for six years, and yet some continue with university for 3 to 4 years to end with a bachelor's degree in their area of specialization. Apart from boarding schools [public, private, subsidized] and day schools [not boarding school-home], other vocational schools are giving short courses for professions and end up with a certificate after a certain period of time, and they are somewhat considered as secondary schools.

Brief historical background for Kinyarwanda teaching and Learning

Teaching is regarded as a continuous process of guiding and facilitating students by providing information, concepts, and adequate support. Effective teaching involves using various methods and strategies to make students understand and apply knowledge learnt to

solve trending issues, and it is known as learning. Teaching impacts learning through the application of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that are strengthened by our experiences.

Karani (1986) wrote that the teaching and learning of Kinyarwanda has shown a notably positive evolution throughout its history and Rwandan culture. To preserve the culture of any country, we need to teach its national language. This is to ensure that a transmission of culture across generations remains relevant. According to Tabaro (2014, p. 25-26), it would be incorrect to mean that in Rwanda education was not there before before 1900s. Although modern schools were not there before the arrival of missionaries, we know that Rwandans were formally educated and trained to be heroes and country defenders (males), sexual satisfaction and better family makers (females) through Itorero "Civic Academy" and Urubohero "Weaving room" (Niyomugabo,2015).

According to Sibomana (2010), after Rwanda's independence in 1962, the Constitution of November 1962, as revised in December 1978 and in June 1991, stressed that Kinyarwanda is the National and official language. Since that time, Kinyarwanda was used as a language of instruction in primary one up to Primary nine, as revised to primary six, and in secondary schools, French was used as the official language and language of instruction. Since 2008, English has joined that pathway to be a language of instruction. But Kinyarwanda remained there as the only national language of Rwanda, as the Constitution of 2003 states. Now that Kinyarwanda is taught as a subject in all levels of education from primary up to university, to preserve the country's history and culture.

Previous studies on pragmatics and language learning

Language learning and acquisition count on many factors that influence individuals' ability to acquire and use language effectively. Some of these factors include environmental factors (exposure to a certain language), socio-cultural context (words and expressions, taboos ([Dos and Don'ts]) to shape language development from a young age to adulthood.

Other researchers, such as Garnham (2019), depicted cognitive mechanisms of language processing, like phonetics, phonology, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics to be the sources of language comprehension. Moreover, we cannot forget the impact of individual differences in life, such as age, aptitude, motivation, and documentation, among others, on language learning outcomes. Going beyond this, we can also look at the interaction between biological effects, cognitive effects, and socio-cultural effects while learning a language.

In the United Kingdom, pragmatics is greatly involved in teaching and learning. Students focus on communicative competence and context-based language use. Shiyab (2007, p.238) confirms that learning a language involves looking at it in different corners and brings one thing, which he described as an exposure to amalgamation. Teaching pragmatics must match the real-life situation by giving explicit communication in classroom scenarios. This approach helps students mirror a language in different contexts.

Teaching Language registers in a classroom setting

In France, language registers are prominently considered as a focus on formal and academic language through many structured lessons and literary texts analysis known as "Roman-Novels" to emphasize distinctions between various levels of formality in both written and spoken language. Students grow up with an evidence-based map of how one statement can have different expressions. They are given practical exercises that arouse their interest in context and situations. They can discriminate with formal writing, casual conversation, and professional contexts. According to Celce-Murcia & Olshtain (2000, p.3) confirms that teaching a language must combine a discourse (register) and a context (pragmatics); otherwise, communication may be hindered, because a language is deeply encompassing both the appropriate register and the pragmatic context in which it occurs.

Role of Pragmatics in teaching and learning

In linguistics, pragmatics is considered a branch that explores how language functions in various contexts. By this inference, we mean the time, place, and reason why a language is used. According to Menchik & Tian (2008), pragmatics put words into various contexts by interpreting a language based on social norms, situational cues, and communication guidelines, which are essential for effective communication, teaching, and learning.

In the Rwandan secondary education system, pragmatics is not represented as the formal curriculum shows. This omission means that students are not largely exposed to the appropriateness of language use in various contexts, and they choose to only focus on their own meaning without considering the origin, context used to express a certain idea. For example, when we analyze the way "Ibishegu" is addressed today, we notice that it is used to mean "words that turn around sexuality," and this is taken as nonsense and taboo in Rwandan culture when used publicly. Back in history, the word existed, and it has different social contexts or how to interpret communicative nuances, attributed to it. With IRST (1990) in a Kinyarwanda dictionary, they explained that "Igishegu" is used to talk about "an official beggar in Ryangombe worship". As per the notice, a language is born, grows, and dies. This means "Igishegu" found another additional meaning, "sexuality focus". We can finally note that using such a word is not bad, but we must consider the pragmatics principle by which context and social norms are applied. Students must critically understand, interpret, and apply language in various social situations, and these are pragmatics' attributes. Levinson (1983, pp. 15-30) underscores the importance of integrating pragmatic principles into education to help students access social interactions, communication, and academic discourse more effectively.

Role of language registers in Teaching and Learning

Stockwell (2002, p.9) said, "Register can be defined either narrowly or broadly. The narrow definition sees register simply as an occupational variety of language. So, for example, teachers, computer programmers, mechanics, or sociolinguists tend to have characteristic ways of speaking which involve certain particular word-choices and grammatical constructions." This means that different styles or varieties of language are used in various contexts, such as formal, informal, and specialized registers, to express a certain opinion. A

clear understanding of language registers can help students adapt to different communicative situations, and with confidence, while expressing any idea.

Cognitive and communicative approaches to Pragmatics and language registers in Kinyarwanda instruction

The study employs a cognitive and communicative theoretical framework to investigate the role of pragmatics and language registers in Kinyarwanda teaching and learning. This framework integrates elements of cognitive psychology, which explores how individuals acquire and process language skills in everyday communication, whereas the communicative approach emphasizes the social and contextual aspects of language use in a formal setting. With the Cognitive theory, Carruthers (2002) says that it is associated with how natural language is involved in human thinking. This would mean how teachers and students internalize and apply pragmatic principles in their language practices to develop their competence in Kinyarwanda and any other language. For the communicative theory, Jacobson et al (2013) state that a language must be learnt to be used in different situational and contextual factors to determine appropriate application and effective comprehension.

Language registers levels and examples

According to Martin (2001, p. 167), a new language involves something to do with the society it is being used in a society, and this must take into account different methodologies of language learning. Within concepts used to learn a language, genre and register are some systematic ways to teach a language.

With genre, we must consider types of text and discourse, such as reports, narratives, dialogues, and structures of a given context, which reflect language registers whereby a formal or informal variation helps communicators to adapt their communication to different situations and audiences, and these are linked to the culture of that country. For example, the way someone talks at the market, at school, or in church must be different to mean that some good commands and grammatical patterns are introduced appropriately. Although most of the researchers agree on two major language registers, like formal and informal, there are other forms of language registers under which an exchange of spoken and written language occurs. Authier and Meunier (1972, p.57) confirmed that language registers are determined by the audience and the situation. We find them in statements like 'familiar' or 'very familiar' in one context, and 'neutral', or 'Very formal' in the umbrella of formal (very formal, formal), and informal (familiar, neutral, and very familiar).

Register	Definition	Examples
Very formal register (Formal)	<p>The formal register is mainly used in official settings such as literary works, academic writings, professional meetings, and reports, among others.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characterized by complex sentences or literary expressions known as figures of speech (in a written manner). • It doesn't use grammatical contractions or casual expressions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We would like to request an extension on the deadline of our presentation report. • My advice to you is that "If speech is silver, silence is gold."
Informal	<p>The informal register is typically used in casual or familiar settings with friends and family.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is called informal because it employs familiar words and abbreviations. • Use of short and simple sentences and many contractions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hey, have you brought my TV? • I can't wait to visit you!
The everyday register (neutral)	<p>The everyday register is always used in a neutral language (written, spoken), which is correct for conversation and simple readings.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no effort to the neutral register; sentences are normal and simple without ambiguity. • It is used by the common people in a conversation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My mother bought a new car. • In September every year, schools resume teaching.
Technical register/Jargon	<p>It is one of the informal ways of language registers used by people of the same interest, age, and familiarity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses a lot of jargon in speech and intonation. 	<p>He told him, "I cannot run fast, I have to take control of my balls!"</p> <p><i>He mentioned that the term 'ball' serves as both a metaphor and a reference to the male genital."</i></p>

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- Used in specialized fields like drivers, students, cooks, divers, etc.
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ALL forms

A comparison of the **very formal, formal, informal, and neutral**

- I will go to the market to buy mangoes. (neutral)
 - I will go to the market and get fresh mangoes. (**formal**)
 - I'll go to the market and buy yellow mangoes (informal)
 - I will visit the market to purchase some fresh mangoes. (**very formal**)
-

Importance of pragmatics and language registers in teaching and learning

Pragmatics and language registers play a very central role in teaching and learning because they get learners' attention in communicative competence and cultural understanding. Pragmatics plays on contextual analysis; learners interpret and produce language appropriately according to social and cultural norms, whereas language registers teach learners to be familiar with variations in contexts and audiences, whether formal, informal, or technical, and they adapt themselves for any communicative purpose.

Bardovi-Harlig (1996, p. 25) emphasizes that learning is copying. This means that when learners are exposed to pragmatic scenarios in a classroom, "they are provided with models and encouraged to try their own requests through a series of role plays based on those scenarios." On one hand, pragmatics helps teachers to not only teach grammar and vocabulary but also develop learners' communicative skills among themselves and the community. On the other hand, educators will empower learners to communicate effectively across different situations. Language registers, which foster their linguistic flexibility, freedom of speech, and cultural sensitivity, which is a very good connection between educators, learners, and researchers.

Difficulties in acquiring the mother tongue

According to Woldemariam (2007), research conducted in Ethiopia shows several challenges facing mother tongue education. These challenges include a shortage of financial and human resources, the presence of numerous languages and dialects, and inconsistent strategies to address these issues. He also added some attitudes within the society towards mother-tongue education, where they think that knowledge is measured by the foreign language and various pedagogical problems.

Similarly to this, in Rwanda, Kinyarwanda faces challenges due to a preference for foreign languages like English and French, which are often perceived as more prestigious

languages. This preference can lead to a devaluation of Kinyarwanda, affecting its use and cultural significance. To address this, there is a need for efforts to emphasize the importance of Kinyarwanda and to provide better support for its education and preservation. Implementing effective teaching strategies on pragmatics and language registers can generate a rapid appreciation for Kinyarwanda and its continued relevance in both educational and social contexts. Marginalizing Kinyarwanda and its speakers. By confusing it with backwardness and limited usefulness compared to English, which is taken as a sign of power, smartness, and several other advantages has effects in the Rwandan community. "For instance, it has resulted in some people being 'ashamed' of Kinyarwanda and identifying more with English." (Sibomana & Uwambayinema, 2016, p.30).

METHODOLOGY

The study addresses critical gaps that are in language education for Rwandan secondary schools to impact both teachers and students in the application of Kinyarwanda while teaching and learning. By exploring how the effective use of formal Kinyarwanda, both in speech and orthography, affects the students' performance, the research contributed significantly to educational practices and policy recommendations in Rwanda. On one hand, pragmatics in educational settings has the emphasis on the understanding of when, where, and why formal Kinyarwanda is used, and on the other hand, language registers are fundamental for effective teaching and learning. The findings of this research have detailed the challenges faced by teachers and students due to the lack of learning materials and training specifically focused on pragmatics and language registers.

Research Design

According to Gupta & Gupta (2022) a research comes from two words, 'Re' and 'Search', which means to search or build upon existing facts or bring new ones to answer questions through a scientific method. To examine the role of pragmatics and language registers in Rwandan secondary schools, we employed a quantitative research design that utilized structured observation and questionnaires. Data analysis from a sample of students and teachers across the country provided a clear picture of practices and fundamental perceptions. Our focus is to have a look at language use and teaching strategies that will practically guide the sovereignty of Kinyarwanda in education and communication at large.

Respondents of the Study

The study involved 250 students and 15 Kinyarwanda language teachers from five purposively selected secondary schools across Rwanda, representing all major regions. The participating schools included GS Kinyinya (Kigali City), GS Kirwa (Gicumbi District, Northern Province), ES Ruramira (Kayonza District, Eastern Province), ES Rubengera (Karongi District, Western Province), and GS Byimana (Ruhango District, Southern Province). These schools are of nine- and twelve-year basic Education (9/12YBE). From each school, 50 students were purposively sampled based on their exposure to Kinyarwanda language instruction, totaling 250 participants. Additionally, three Kinyarwanda language teachers from each school were selected, making a total of 15 teachers. The study concentrated on secondary-level education,

excluding primary and tertiary levels, to reflect only the experiences of language education in secondary schools.

Research instruments

Two main approaches were employed: structured classroom observations and semi-structured questionnaires. Classroom observations took place over two weeks in each school, focusing on language use, teacher-student interactions, and the application of pragmatic principles and language registers. Each observation session lasted between 45 and 60 minutes, aligning with the typical lesson length.

The questionnaires were designed for both students and teachers. Student questionnaires assessed their familiarity with different language registers, ability to interpret context, and difficulties encountered when using formal Kinyarwanda. Teacher questionnaires examined instructional strategies, awareness of pragmatics, and perceptions of students' language proficiency. To ensure validity and relevance, the instruments were reviewed by two language education experts, who confirmed their alignment with the study's objectives and the national curriculum framework.

Statistical tools and treatment

A mixed-methods approach was used to analyze data from teachers and students. Quantitative data from closed-ended questionnaire items were analyzed using descriptive statistics, frequencies, and percentages processed through SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) to ensure accuracy. Key variables included familiarity with language registers, usage of formal Kinyarwanda, and instructional strategies reported by teachers. Qualitative data from open-ended responses and observation notes were analyzed using thematic analysis. Responses were manually coded to identify patterns in teaching, pragmatic competence, and language use challenges while addressing pragmatics and language registers in Kinyarwanda classrooms.

Research Framework

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The table summarize the key findings related to the research objectives and questions, providing a foundation for the discussion towards the role of Pragmatics and language registers in teaching and learning Kinyarwanda language in Secondary schools, the extent to which Pragmatics and language registers are applied in teaching and learning Kinyarwanda and last but not least the consequences of non-application/use of Pragmatics and language registers while teaching and learning Kinyarwanda Language in secondary schools. A presentation of findings with tables, figures, and graphs was used to provide step by step a balanced approach to use between a Kinyarwanda formal instructional language and practical skills needed to match the context-based language use in communication.

Table 1: Groups of Respondents and the Aspects of Assessment

Respondent Group	Aspect Assessed	Frequency	Percent (%)
Teachers (Total = 15)			
	• Formal integration of pragmatics into the curriculum	2	13.3%
	• Use of informal activities/extra-curricular to enhance pragmatics (e.g., <i>igitaramo, itorerero</i>)	3	20.0%
	• Awareness of pragmatic concepts in teaching	5	33.3%
	• Formal training in pragmatics and language registers	2	13.3%
Students (Total = 250)			
	• Exposure to pragmatic instruction in a classroom setting	38	15.2%
	• Understanding of language register use in various contexts	33	13.2%

As shown in Table 1, there is limited emphasis on pragmatics and language registers in classroom instruction, with only 13.3% of teachers reporting formal integration into the curriculum. Informal activities such as *igitaramo* (cultural party) are occasionally used by 20% of teachers but lack regularity and consistent application. While 33.3% of teachers demonstrate some awareness of pragmatic concepts, most lack formal training, which contributes to students' low exposure (15.2%) and limited understanding (13.2%) of appropriate register use.

Pragmatics as a formal lesson remains minimal in Rwandan secondary schools and is often applied at a very low level, typically focusing on simple notions like "Ntibavuga bavuga" ("What not to say versus What to say"). Although teachers show some awareness of pragmatic concepts, the absence of structured training limits their familiarity with updated approaches and practical implementation. Consequently, students develop limited skills in understanding

and applying pragmatic principles within their learning environment. The smaller the number, indicates low implementation rather than outright rejection or opposition:

- Weak or unclear guidance in the curriculum about where and how to teach pragmatics.
- Limited teacher confidence or training in applying pragmatics explicitly.
- Lack of resources or materials to support formal instruction in this area.

Table 2: Register Type, Coverage, and Impact on Student Proficiency in Kinyarwanda

Register Type	Profile View (Teachers and Students)	Aspect Measured	Coverage in Instruction (%)
Formal Register & Pragmatics	Teachers introduce selectively; students are underexposed	Academic communication, assessments	40%
Informal Register & Pragmatics	Limited practice; students lack application spaces	Social interaction, expression	45%
Everyday Register	Common in daily use; both groups rely on it	Functional communication	52%
Mixed/Technical Register	Frequent code-mixing; low-structured teaching	Oral fluency, contextual jargon	40%

As shown in Table 2, the Everyday Register receives the highest instructional coverage (52%) and remains central to both teaching and student interaction, though often without structured materials. Formal and informal registers receive moderate attention, yet teaching often lacks depth in contextual usage, such as understanding the role of time, setting, and audience in "Ikeshamvugo" (formal speech). Meanwhile, the Mixed/Technical Register, though commonly used due to multilingual exposure, lacks intentional instruction—resulting in reduced oral proficiency and unstructured code-switching that weakens communicative clarity in both classroom and real-world contexts.

Table 3: Teacher vs. Student Views on Pragmatics and Language Registers and What Happens When They're Not Used/Non-application

Aspect	Teacher View	Student View	What Happens If Not Used / Non-Application
Formal Teaching	Rarely included in lessons (10%)	Not clearly taught (10%)	Students can't use the right language in different settings
Use of Role-Play/Cultural Tasks	Sometimes used, not often (20%)	Some experience, not regular	Missed practice using real-life language
Awareness	Some know it matters (35%), few are trained	Most don't know about it (15%)	Poor communication and misunderstanding
In-Class Use	Not part of daily teaching	Learn by guessing or copying	Weak skills in formal/informal language use

The data in Table 3 highlights a significant gap in the instruction and integration of pragmatics and language registers in Kinyarwanda education. Only 27% of students demonstrate high proficiency, while 25% struggle specifically with the use of formal Kinyarwanda, indicating that pragmatic competence is not being effectively nurtured through the current curriculum. Among teachers, only 40% show strong proficiency in teaching formal registers, and just 5% successfully integrate pragmatic concepts into instruction—often due to limitations in their educational background or vocabulary range. This shortfall directly affects student development, as the lack of explicit, contextual language instruction weakens both language competence and communicative effectiveness in formal and informal settings.

Table 4: Recommendations based on key findings

Recommendation	Support (%)	Priority
Add Pragmatics to the Kinyarwanda Curriculum	80%	Long-Term
Increase Practical Language Use (e.g., activities)	75%	Short-Term
Teach Language Registers at All Secondary Levels	70%	Medium-Term
Provide Ongoing Teacher Training in Kinyarwanda	65%	Short-Term

The majority of participants (80%) strongly support adding pragmatics to the Kinyarwanda curriculum, highlighting its importance in real communication. Additionally, 75% favor more practical activities, while 70% and 65% stress the need for register instruction across levels and ongoing teacher training, respectively. The table highlights a strong support for integrating pragmatics and language registers into Kinyarwanda education, especially through curriculum updates, practical activities, and teacher training. While some recommendations can be addressed in the short term (e.g., training, activities), others require longer-term planning, such as curriculum reform.

Table 5: Strategies for Integrating Pragmatics and Language Registers in Teaching and Learning

Phase	Action	Details	Expected Outcome
Investigate	Assess Current Practices of Kinyarwanda and language registers	Conduct surveys and interviews with teachers and students to understand current methods and challenges regarding the Kinyarwanda status nowadays.	Gain background information for existing practices and gaps.
Plan	Develop a Comprehensive Curriculum that allows the use of pragmatics and language registers.	Design a curriculum that incorporates formal pragmatics and language registers with specific learning objectives and activities that allow students to navigate both pragmatics and language registers.	Ensure a systematic inclusion of pragmatics in all lessons of Kinyarwanda.
Evaluate	Pilot and assess the Effectiveness benefits through the	Implement the new curriculum in a few classes, and collect feedback from	Identify strengths and areas for improvement in the

	integration of pragmatics and language registers	students and teachers about areas of strength and weakness.	Kinyarwanda curriculum teaching.
Implement	Roll out and Train Educators about pragmatics and language registers	Fully integrate the revised curriculum into all classes and provide training workshops for teachers to better understand the reasons.	Evaluate overall teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes for a common success in proficiency and performance.

The findings presented in Table 5 outline a systematic framework for integrating pragmatics and language registers in teaching and learning of Kinyarwanda. The results emphasize a four-phase approach, beginning with investigating current practices through surveys and interviews to establish existing gaps. Planning then focuses on designing a comprehensive curriculum that incorporates pragmatics and language registers into specific learning objectives and activities. The evaluation phase highlights piloting the revised curriculum in selected classes to gather feedback on its strengths and weaknesses. Finally, the implementation phase stresses the full integration of the curriculum across classrooms and the training of teachers to ensure effective delivery. Collectively, this strategy is expected to strengthen the systematic inclusion of pragmatics in Kinyarwanda instruction, improve curriculum effectiveness, and enhance student outcomes in terms of both proficiency and performance.

Conclusion

This study has highlighted a critical need to strengthen the teaching of pragmatics and language registers in Rwandan secondary schools, especially within the Kinyarwanda curriculum. Addressing this gap requires structured curriculum reforms, strategic collaboration among educational and cultural institutions, and ongoing teacher development. Limitations include the study's limited sample size and geographic scope, which may not fully reflect all schools' practices. Future research should explore student outcomes after implementation and compare effectiveness across different school settings.

Recommendations

To address the gaps in language instruction and enhance communication skills among students, targeted actions are essential at multiple levels. These measures aim to create a more effective and sustainable language learning environment:

- Integrate language components such as pragmatics and registers at all levels of secondary education to ensure consistent and comprehensive learning.
- Support teachers through continuous training to equip them with the necessary skills and resources for effective instruction.
- Promote wider public engagement through media, discussions, and cultural initiatives to reinforce language use beyond the classroom.
- Explore the influence of media and social dynamics on language practices, creating opportunities for partnerships with NGOs and other stakeholders.
- Strengthen language education and communication practices nationwide through collaborative efforts and innovative outreach.

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